

From Cybernetics to Immersivity: Reframing Sound Space in Electroacoustic and Audiovisual Composition

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Abstract. This article examines the evolution of sound space in electroacoustic music from a theoretical and compositional perspective, with a focus on key works by Paulo C. Chagas. It transitions from early paradigms of *musique concrète* and *elektronische Musik* to immersive and telematic environments, articulating sound space as a relational, cognitive-affective field shaped by technologies, listening practices, and socio-political conditions. Drawing on theories of acoustemology, cybernetics, affect, and embodied cognition, the discussion encompasses the cybernetic spatial models of *Migration* and *Projektion*, the immersive ambisonic environment of *Pune Metamorphosis*, and the telematic field-work of *Sound Imaginations*. Electroacoustic sound space is not confined to technical or aesthetic dimensions; it constitutes a cognitive-affective and socio-political field in which composition unfolds as a mode of knowing, a practice of critique, and a poetics of presence.

Keywords: Electroacoustic Music · Sound Space · Acoustemology · Ambisonics · Cybernetics · Immersion · Telematic Composition · Paulo C. Chagas.

1 Introduction – Sound, Space, and Acoustemology

The experience of sound has always been inseparable from space, yet the notion of sound space in electroacoustic music has taken on new critical dimensions in recent decades. No longer constrained by architectural acoustics or stereo imaging, sound space emerges as a relational and dynamic field shaped by listening practices, compositional intent, technological affordances, and affective perception. This article explores this multidimensional concept by tracing its evolution from cybernetic spatial models to immersive compositional ecologies, with reference to a corpus of works developed across Paulo C. Chagas' compositional practice.

Georgina Born's typology of musical space provides an essential entry point. In her analysis of music and sociality, she identifies three coexisting modalities of

space: the phenomenological space of sound (as constituted by its material and perceptual properties), the social space of production and performance, and the relational or networked space shaped by technological mediation and cultural practice [4]. Electroacoustic music, particularly in its post-studio forms, complicates these categories. While much of the early discourse focused on spatialization in a technical sense—diffusion, localization, ambisonics—Born’s emphasis on relationality opens a broader horizon: sound space as a socio-technological construct shaped by interaction, contingency, and emergent systems.

This relational view resonates with Steven Feld’s foundational notion of *acoustemology*—a term that fuses “acoustics” and “epistemology” to propose sound as a way of knowing [25]. Feld’s ethnographic work among the Kaluli of Papua New Guinea revealed how listening is embedded in place, time, and social ontology; rainforest sounds were not only ambient but epistemic—integral to cultural knowledge, orientation, and meaning-making [23,24]. Acoustemology thus emphasizes listening as a situated, embodied, and affectively charged activity. It challenges objectivist approaches to sound by foregrounding the experiential, intuitive, and even spiritual dimensions of auditory perception.

Building on Feld, Tom Rice broadens acoustemology’s scope to include modern and technical soundscapes, from hospital acoustics to urban noise, suggesting that auditory knowledge continues to play a structuring role in contemporary life [34]. His work underscores how listening practices are culturally encoded and politically charged, and how the design of sound environments often reflects asymmetries of power, authority, and access.

In parallel, Katherine Hayles offers a powerful framework for understanding listening through her concept of the *cognitive nonconscious*. She introduces the idea of *cognitive assemblages*: distributed systems involving human and technical agents whose interaction patterns form a kind of ambient intelligence [30]. From this perspective, listening is not solely a conscious or subjective act; it also involves nonconscious processing—by both biological and machinic systems—situated within planetary-scale networks of cognition and control. This view aligns closely with recent developments in immersive and telematic composition, where signal processing, machine learning, and sensor networks participate in the generation and modulation of sound space.

Drawing from these theoretical paradigms, we propose an understanding of sound space in electroacoustic music as a *cognitive-affective field*: a dynamic and co-constructed territory where perception, emotion, memory, and materiality converge. This field is shaped by the spatial distribution of sound (ambisonics, diffusion), by compositional form (granular textures, feedback loops), and by the listener’s situatedness—whether in a concert hall, a telematic environment, or an immersive installation. In Paulo C. Chagas’ works—from *Migration* to *Projektion*, *Pune Metamorphosis*, and *Sound Imaginations*—sound space functions not as a neutral container but as an active, transformative medium, revealing the resonant interplay between the self, the system, and the environment.

In what follows, we trace the development of this conception through a sequence of compositional case studies and theoretical reflections. We begin by

revisiting early frameworks of spatial thinking in electroacoustic music [38,3,7], before moving on to more experimental articulations that reflect cybernetic, affective, and immersive paradigms.

2 Space in Electroacoustic Music

The electroacoustic paradigm represents a profound shift in the cultural, aesthetic, and technological foundations of music. It has expanded the field of musical creation by introducing a new set of tools—apparatuses—that transform sound perception and production. As Chagas writes [13, p. 19], “With the electroacoustic paradigm, we build the capacity to use apparatuses to produce and move sounds around spaces.” This paradigm is not merely a historical continuation of the instrumental or vocal traditions; it constitutes a new epistemological framework for thinking and composing with sound.

Within this expanded paradigm, two foundational directions emerged after World War II: *musique concrète* in Paris and *elektronische Musik* in Cologne. *Musique concrète*, developed by Pierre Schaeffer, emphasized the use of recorded sounds from the acoustic environment. The tape recorder enabled the isolation of sound objects from their physical sources, allowing them to be manipulated as self-referential sonic materials. This approach was grounded in phenomenology, particularly Husserlian concepts of bracketing and perception, and it introduced the influential distinction between sound object and sound source [35].

On the other hand, *elektronische Musik*, centered at the WDR Studio in Cologne, explored the generation of entirely new sounds using electronic oscillators, sine waves, and noise generators—tools not originally designed for music but repurposed as musical apparatuses. Composers such as Karlheinz Stockhausen constructed sounds from scratch, layering and organizing them through serial and mathematical principles. This school was marked by an aesthetic of purity and control, in contrast to the concrete tradition’s reliance on empirical discovery [39].

Despite their contrasting origins, these schools converged under the umbrella of the electroacoustic paradigm, which dissolves the strict opposition between found and synthetic sounds. What matters is no longer the origin of the sound, but its function within a creative system. The paradigm embraces both reduction and construction, analysis and synthesis. It recognizes that sound can be apprehended in its immediacy or reconstituted as part of a network of virtual relations.

In this context, the practice of *reduced listening* (*écoute réduite*), championed by Schaeffer, is a cornerstone. It calls for a suspension of referential and causal associations, enabling a more abstract and focused attention on the sonic morphology—texture, duration, envelope, and spectral content. *Reduced listening* resonates with Denis Smalley’s theory of *spectromorphology*, which provides a vocabulary for describing and analyzing sound shapes and gestures from a perceptual standpoint [38]. Both approaches prioritize the experience of sound over its source or meaning.

The electroacoustic paradigm not only integrates and transcends vocal and instrumental paradigms but also redefines the very ontology of sound in music. It inaugurates a field of sonic practice in which technological apparatuses are not merely tools but co-creators of meaning. In this framework, sound becomes a medium of thought, a site of exploration, and a material of transformation. Electroacoustic music thus emerges as a ‘laboratory’ of listening, invention, and aesthetic critique—an experimental form of life that reflects, challenges, and reshapes our relationship to sound, space, and technology.

Continuing this exploration, we must consider the electroacoustic studio not merely as a neutral site of production, but as an active component of musical thought and spatial composition. The studio mediates the relationship between the composer, the machinery, and the emerging sonic material. As Chagas has argued elsewhere, electroacoustic music integrates two basic conceptions of sound space: (1) as an embodiment of performance and (2) as an embodiment of composition [7, p. 189].

In the first model—linked to *musique concrète* and the tradition of the loudspeaker orchestra—spatialization is performed live, assigning sound channels to speaker positions in real-time. Here, the loudspeaker functions analogously to a performer, and each concert becomes a unique spatial interpretation. This notion reinforces the aesthetic of space as gesture, where spatial decisions are temporal, contingent, and irreproducible. The variability of loudspeaker configurations from one venue to another introduces a spatial multiplicity, producing a different sonic image with each realization.

In contrast, the second model arises from the serialist tradition of *elektronische Musik*, in which space becomes a compositional parameter—designed, encoded, and fixed within the multichannel tape. Spatial form is treated algorithmically, in line with other parameters such as pitch or rhythm. In this view, sound synthesis and spatial position are intrinsically correlated, and space can function as a structuring principle akin to musical form. This mode of thinking was enabled by technological advances such as the four-track recorder and quadraphonic speaker arrays, which allowed composers to assign sounds to specific positions and simulate movement across the spatial field.

As space became a parametric dimension, electroacoustic music acquired a new tactile quality: sound was no longer simply heard, but perceived as occupying a physical position—a sonic body with boundaries and orientation. This phenomenological shift reframed the experience of electroacoustic music. Space, like timbre, became a semiotic and perceptual vector for meaning, grounding the experience of listening in embodied spatial memory.

The studio, therefore, is not only a site of production but also a conceptual instrument—a resonant chamber where compositional ideas are shaped by the materiality of space, apparatuses, and feedback loops. As Chagas later developed through the notion of circular sound space, this perspective emphasizes movement, rotation, and the recursive shaping of spatial relationships within an immersive listening field [7].

3 Circular Sound Space: *Migration* (1995–97)

The composition of sound space has evolved alongside technological advances that have enabled the creation, manipulation, and projection of sound in multiple dimensions. As explained by Chagas in *Circular Sound Space* [7], the multitrack tape recorder played a foundational role in establishing electroacoustic music as a multilayered medium capable of spatial articulation. This development laid the groundwork for complex sound environments where the spatial location, movement, and layering of sounds became compositional resources.

The WDR Electronic Studio in Cologne became a benchmark for spatial composition in the 1950s. It offered both the technological infrastructure and the architectural design necessary for advanced electroacoustic experimentation. A landmark in spatial music created at WDR is Karlheinz Stockhausen's *Kontakte* (1958–60), one of the most emblematic quadraphonic works of the twentieth century. The studio featured a *Rotationstisch*, a mechanical rotating table used to spin loudspeakers and project sounds dynamically through a four-speaker array—an analog precursor to algorithmic sound movement.

This concept was further developed in *Oktophonie* (1991), where Stockhausen expanded the four-channel format into an eight-channel immersive environment. These works redefined sound projection as an essential compositional parameter and established WDR's studio as a crucible for innovative spatial music.

With the emergence of digital tools, these principles were significantly expanded. As described in *Circular Sound Space* [7], the introduction of Pro Tools and the multichannel capabilities of hard disk recording enabled composers to access, arrange, and transform multiple sound channels in highly flexible ways. Hybrid workflows combining analog tools such as the EMS Synthi 100 with digital environments like Max enabled the programming of complex spatial gestures and the real-time control of twelve-channel diffusion systems.

Migration: 12 channel electronic music (1995-97) [5] was composed in this context. It is performed for an audience surrounded by a circle of 12 loudspeakers, arranged in a manner similar to the numerals of a virtual analog clock. This spatial configuration reflects the architecture of the main production room at the WDR Studio, where a ring of 12 ceiling-mounted speakers provided an immersive listening environment. This setting was instrumental in defining the core spatial ideas of the composition, as Chagas worked there as Sound Director and Composer-in-Residence from 1990 to 1999.

The artistic concept of *Migration* is inspired by Jorge Luis Borges' short story "The Library of Babel," which imagines an infinite labyrinth of hexagonal rooms. This metaphor became the conceptual and poetic basis for a circular, endless, and non-hierarchical sound space. The notion of "migration" also serves as a metaphor for the constant displacement and spectral transformation of sound material through the loudspeaker constellation.

The concept of circular sound space in *Migration* is founded on the correlation of spectral transformation with spatial diffusion, as Chagas describes: "the concept of circular sound space develops a 12-channel polyphony by correlating

spectral transformation to sound spatialization” [9, p. 180]. The spatial design is structured around two fundamental principles:

1. *Decomposition in static sound spaces* – Spectral components are separated and assigned to specific speaker locations or geometric constellations involving 3, 4, 6, or 12 channels.
2. *Movement in dynamic sound spaces* – Sounds rotate and move between speakers in patterned ways, forming sonic trajectories that create polygons such as hexagons, triangles, squares, or twelve-sided rings.

The 12-channel configuration is sometimes conceived as two interlocking hexagons—a spatial metaphor inspired by Jorge Luis Borges’ short story “The Library of Babel”, in which hexagonal rooms extend infinitely in all directions, forming a structure of recursive and labyrinthine architecture. This conception informed both the compositional and spatial strategies of the piece, allowing the geometric logic of rotation to be metaphorically aligned with a broader epistemic vision. This approach is visually represented in Figure 1, which illustrates the dual-hexagon configuration and its rotational trajectories within the circular sound field.

Fig. 1. Dual-hexagon spatial design in *Migration*, showing 12-channel speaker configuration and geometric rotation system.

Special attention was given to different types of rotation: in-phase rotation, where all spectral components circulate together; counter-rotation, in which parts move in opposite directions; and irregular, fragmented rotations that produce sudden shifts and asymmetries [9, p. 181]. These operations were programmed using Max to control real-time displacements and modulation parameters, often driven by algorithmic sequences or spatial envelopes.

As summarized in Chagas’ book *Unsayable Music*, “The audience is enveloped by a virtual polyphony of twelve channels, organized as spatial patterns and trajectories that generate sound masses and textures, comparable to moving

constellations” [9, p. 181]. The resulting space supports both analytical listening—through decomposition—and affective immersion—through rotational flux and spectral transformation.

4 Cybernetic Circularity: *Projektion* (2000)

The piece *Projektion: 12 channel electronic music* (2000) [6] explores the notion of circularity as a cybernetic principle of composition, rooted in analog-era thinking about rotation, feedback loops, temporal modulation, and automated rotation. Its aesthetic is inspired by concepts from systems theory and second-order cybernetics—particularly Heinz von Foerster’s notion of non-trivial machines [27] and Niklas Luhmann’s theory of autopoietic systems [32]. The origin of the piece was entirely accidental. During the experimental phase of *Migration* in 1995, a computer crash occurred while loading a sample of a female voice. Instead of rebooting, the system looped a short fragment—approximately 100 milliseconds—ten times per second. Rather than discard this failure, Chagas routed the audio into the 12-channel analog-digital spatialization system developed in the WDR studio with sound engineer Volker Müller.

The interaction between the sample and the spatial envelopes, which were set to 72 milliseconds, created a rhythmic misalignment. The result was a perceptual interplay of accentuation, rotation, and instability that the composer immediately recorded in Pro Tools. The resulting spatialization system—illustrated in Figure 2—relied on 12 VCA channels that functioned as time windows. These were modulated using Max patches and controlled rotation in a clockwise direction. The envelope of each window, derived from the Synthi 100 and converted to MIDI, determined amplitude variation across channels, creating a sense of continuous spatial movement. The rotation system became a sonic “machine,” simulating constant circular displacement while introducing micro-instabilities between the loop length and the envelope window.

Projektion was not conceived as a conventional electroacoustic composition but as an evolving structure of algorithmic transformations. The original loop-based recording became the “Urstruktur”—a raw twelve-track texture that was subjected to five additional processing methods: Feedback, Delay, SinusFilter, ChaosFilter, and SinusFilterEnd [11]. Each transformation was algorithmically programmed and applied simultaneously across all twelve tracks without the use of montage. The result was six mixed structures (*Projektion 01–06*), each building different layers of spectral and spatial polyphony.

For instance, the feedback transformation was implemented using Pro Tools buses that looped each output into the next, completing a cycle from channel 12 back to 1. A short impulse inserted into the loop triggered twelve-channel spatial feedback. These loops generated harmonic overtones and rhythmic pulses that diverged from the original loop, forming a complex timbral architecture. The delay structure, on the other hand, introduced temporal shifts based on logarithmic scaling of delay times—from 12.5 ms upward—modulated in real-time using Pro Tools automation.

Each of the six 12-channel layers was later combined in two different formats:

1. *Projektion 12-channel electronic music*, a fixed-media piece mixing all layers into a unified 72-track composition (17:28).
2. *Projektion 12-channel sound installation*, an infinite loop that sequentially presents the six layers as an immersive sonic environment (104:48).

Ultimately, *Projektion* enacts the principle of cybernetic circularity—an ongoing re-entry of system output into system input that shapes perception through recursive variation. As Luhmann and von Foerster have emphasized, such systems are non-trivial: they evolve through internal complexity rather than external commands. The sonic result is an autopoietic polyphony—a space that listens to itself and alters its course through repetition, displacement, and feedback.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the 12-channel spatialization and rotation system in *Projektion*, showing loop playback, amplitude envelopes, Max control patches, and speaker layout. Drawing by Volker Müller (See [11]).

5 Embodied Violence: Sound, Torture, and Affect in *The Refrigerator* (2014)

The electroacoustic paradigm not only extends the sonic possibilities of music but also uncovers the darker dimensions of sound's material power. Among its most disturbing manifestations is the use of sound as a weapon—an instrument of torture, control, and dehumanization.

In this context, sound ceases to be a communicative or aesthetic medium and becomes a spatial force that vibrates the body, invades subjectivity, and obliterates the distinction between inner and outer worlds. As Georgina Born [4] has argued, sound space is inherently social, relational, and embedded in systems of power that shape perception and bodily experience.

In *Sound, Truth, and Paradigm*, Paulo C. Chagas frames this within the “vibration-centered model” of the electroacoustic paradigm: “The practice of torture using sound and music shows that within the electroacoustic paradigm exists a vibration-centered model that produces the presence of a ubiquitous, invisible vibrating power, eliminating subjectivity” [13, p. 22]. This insight resonates with Suzanne Cusick’s work on sonic torture in U.S. military detention centers. Her notion of an “acoustemology of detention” describes how sound is used not simply to hurt but to destroy the conditions of personhood [22]. Such deformations of relationality—where one’s voice, silence, and interiority are colonized—represent a sonic annihilation of subjectivity.

As Cusick notes, loud music and other manipulations of the acoustic environments “disrupted prisoners” use of hearing and vocalization both to locate themselves in intelligible worlds and to create relationships with those worlds” [22, p. 276]. This destruction is not metaphorical but physiological: vibration invades the body from within, establishing a totalizing acoustical regime in which the prisoner is rendered vulnerable, isolated, and voiceless.

Paulo C. Chagas’ digital oratorio *The Refrigerator* (2014) [8] emerges from this intersection of personal history and sonic critique. The piece reflects on his own experience as a 17-year-old political prisoner in Brazil. Arrested in 1971 during the military dictatorship, he was confined in a torture chamber known as the *geladeira* [refrigerator]—a small, acoustically isolated room plunged in darkness and freezing air.³ Different kinds of noises and sounds—howling oscillators, rumbling generators, distorted radio signals, motorcycle-like sounds—shot from loudspeakers, invisible behind the walls. The electronic sounds filled the dark space and overwhelmed his body for three long days [12].

The refrigerator was designed not to leave marks. Its cruelty was its invisibility. Sound violated the body and mind with no visible trace of damage, performing what Cusick describes as an “ultimate violence” that “blasts away all sense of privacy, leaving in its place a feeling of paradoxically unprivate isolation” [22, p. 276]. The oratorio stages this traumatic experience as a multidimensional composition for singers, ensemble, live-electronics, and visual projection, tran-

³ The use of acoustically isolated, freezing rooms—commonly referred to as “refrigerators”—was a form of sensory deprivation and psychological torture documented in Brazil during the military dictatorship. This technique was part of a broader repertoire of coercive methods disseminated globally through U.S. military and intelligence training programs during the Cold War, including those described in CIA interrogation manuals and taught at the School of the Americas. For comprehensive documentation, see McCoy (2006) and Rejali (2007). References: McCoy, Alfred W. *A Question of Torture: CIA Interrogation, from the Cold War to the War on Terror*. New York: Metropolitan Books, 2006. Rejali, Darius. *Torture and Democracy*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2007.

scending denunciation to explore metaphysical questions of suffering, memory, and transcendence [12].

The acoustic space of the torture room becomes a dark mirror of immersive sound practices. It is an anti-concert hall—a site where listening is no longer voluntary or aesthetic, but coercive, embodied, and existential. *The Refrigerator* reconstitutes this violence within an artistic framework, transforming the annihilation of subjectivity into an exploration of resilience. Across eight scenes—from “The Darkness of Ignorance” to “Peace: Music that Lives Un-Sung”—the oratorio follows a journey from disintegration toward illumination. Torture is presented not simply as a historical event or political instrument, but as a challenge to reconstitute subjectivity through creative, spiritual, and artistic resistance [12,8].

From this perspective, *the vibrational model of subjectivity* becomes more than a theoretical lens: it is a lived reality, revealed through both personal experience and artistic transfiguration. The testimonies analyzed by Cusick demonstrate how forced vibration annihilates relationality and interiority [22], while Paulo C. Chagas’ experience in the *geladeira* underscores how sound can obliterate the boundaries of self without leaving visible marks. In both cases, subjectivity is fractured by acoustical violence, reduced to fragments that must be reassembled again and again.

Yet these insights also invite us to look beyond the past. The acoustemology of detention foreshadows a broader *acoustemology of surveillance*. Today, algorithmic listening systems, AI-driven monitoring, and sonic crowd-control devices extend the same vibrational logics of domination into everyday environments. Sound becomes not only a tool of spectacular violence but also a subtle medium of governance, where listening is captured, analyzed, and weaponized.

What is at stake is the future of immersion itself. The same vibrational forces that can annihilate subjectivity can also sustain intimacy, creativity, and collective presence. Recognizing this ambivalence is essential for artists and researchers: immersive sound practices demand ethical vigilance, for they carry the potential both to heal and to harm, to create spaces of resonance and resistance, or to reproduce systems of terror and control.

6 Expanding Immersivity: *Pune Metamorphosis* (2023) and the Spatial Aesthetics of Ambisonics

Ambisonics represents a significant evolution in the spatialization of sound, re-framing sound space not as a projection from point sources but as an immersive, spherical field that envelops the listener. Unlike traditional stereo or channel-based surround formats, ambisonics encodes the directional components of sound as a holistic field, enabling dynamic manipulation of perspective and orientation. This spatial technique allows composers to think not just in terms of localization but of continuous, fluid movement within a perceptual sound sphere.

Pune Metamorphosis (2023) by Paulo C. Chagas realizes this spatial paradigm through a collaborative composition created in SuperCollider for ambisonic sound

and immersive 3D video. The work was commissioned by the TU Studio (Technische Universität Berlin – Audiokommunikation), supported by a Fulbright scholarship, and sponsored by the Humboldt Forum Foundation and the Berlin State Museums. It was later presented as a permanent installation in the *Hörraum* at the Humboldt Forum in Berlin. The core material consists of ambisonic field recordings and 360-degree video footage captured in Pune, India, in 2019 as part of Chagas’ research project *Sound Imaginations*. These recordings—from Pune’s city streets, temples, and public spaces—were transformed using real-time granular synthesis and projected through a third-order ambisonics array, forming a cohesive audiovisual exploration of spiritual, urban, and acoustic ecologies. The piece was co-created with programmer and artist Konstantin Fontaine, who developed the granular synthesis engine and spatial algorithms.

For the installation at the Humboldt Forum in Berlin, Paulo C. Chagas produced a third sound space layer featuring bass flute sounds played by Cássia Carrascoza, extracted from a recording of the piece *I Hear You Breathe* (Chagas 2022) [14], which were electronically processed and spatialized using wave field synthesis.⁴ Additionally, Chagas utilized the six monitors installed in the *Hörraum* to create an immersive audiovisual layer featuring the 360-degree video footage captured in Pune. In the *Hörraum*, the work is exhibited as an audiovisual installation combining the ambisonic soundscape, the WFS bass-flute layer, and the 360-degree video distributed across six monitors.⁵

The graphic score of *Pune Metamorphosis* reflects its structural and morphological complexity. The score is not written in conventional notation but consists of visual mappings of sound events and spatial trajectories. It guides the behavior of sonic textures, densities, and movements, offering performers and programmers a conceptual framework. This visual framework is presented in Figure 3, which depicts the graphic score of *Pune Metamorphosis*, highlighting spatial trajectories and granular texture behaviors over time.

Granular synthesis plays a central role in the work’s sonic and spatial design. As described by Barry Truax [40], granular synthesis operates by assembling streams of sound “grains”—brief sonic events typically between 1–100 milliseconds in duration—which can be organized into clouds, textures, and rhythmic patterns. In *Pune Metamorphosis*, grains are spatialized through models such as:

⁴ Wave Field Synthesis (WFS) is a spatial audio rendering technique that employs large loudspeaker arrays to synthesize a virtual sound field, allowing the perception of sound sources at arbitrary positions, including outside the physical array. The *Hörraum* is equipped with a fifth-order ambisonics system consisting of 36 loudspeakers, complemented by additional speakers/subwoofers to reach a total of 45, and a WFS setup comprising 24 panels, each containing 24 loudspeakers.

⁵ Independent of the installation, two video versions of *Pune Metamorphosis* were subsequently produced: (1) *Pune Metamorphosis – version #1* [15], a binaural reduction of the ambisonic version with 360-degree video; (2) *Pune Metamorphosis – version #2* [16], a binaural reduction of the ambisonic version with 360-degree video plus WFS layer with bass flute sounds.

Fig. 3. Graphic score of *Pune Metamorphosis*, indicating spatial trajectories and granular texture behaviors over time. Drawn by Eren Utku as part of the project collaboration.

- *Dots*: point-source grains diffused to discrete locations in the sphere
- *Lines*: linear sweeps across horizontal or vertical planes
- *Swarms*: clusters of grains with dynamic randomization
- *Figures*: structured spatial forms like spirals and helices evolving with spectral transformation

The score informs the real-time behavior of these elements through SuperCollider programming. The morphology of each texture is modulated by parameters such as grain density, envelope shape, delay, pitch shift, and spatial trajectory. These parameters interact algorithmically, creating continuously evolving spatial textures.

A short version of the work was later extracted from the original under the title *Pune Metamorphosis: Shiva's Resonance* (2024) [18]. This audiovisual adaptation focuses on two sacred Shiva temples in Pune, using 3D video and ambisonic sound recordings captured in 2019. Rather than introducing new sonic material, the excerpt draws attention to the perceptual dimension of granular synthesis already present in the larger work—unfolding microtemporal textures that expose the layers of resonance, ritual, and acoustic presence embedded in the original recordings.

Pune Metamorphosis exemplifies immersive telematic composition. Its ambisonic field becomes a shared acoustic body that collapses physical distance and reconstructs presence through sound. It is a paradigmatic example of how space can be generated—not merely occupied—through collaborative listening and computational design.

7 Audiovisual and Telematic Immersion: *Sound Imaginations* (2024)

Sound Imaginations is a long-term interdisciplinary project initiated and directed by Paulo C. Chagas between 2016 and 2024, with key phases of research, fieldwork, and artistic production. Its main objective was to explore global cultures of listening and their articulation through immersive audiovisual and telematic compositions [17]. The project draws from sound studies, phenomenology, media theory, and contemporary music practices. It culminated in the film *Sound Imaginations: Telematic Immersion* (2024), created in collaboration with Brazilian flutist and researcher Cássia Carrascoza [20].

The theoretical foundation for the project is grounded in the idea that listening is a culturally situated and transformative activity, not merely the passive reception of sound. Building on Michel Chion’s triadic model—causal, semantic, and *reduced listening* [21]—and further inspired by Jean-Luc Nancy’s notion of “listening as resonance” [33], *Sound Imaginations* proposes an expanded form of listening as an epistemic and aesthetic act. In this perspective, sound is not only heard but inhabited, inviting listeners to engage in situated, embodied practices of perception and reflection.

Central to the project was the notion of *listening cultures*, as theorized by Holger Schulze [36]. Schulze describes listening not as a purely biological or individual faculty, but as a culturally conditioned mode of attention—shaped by language, environment, education, media, and ritual. These configurations—what Schulze calls *listening cultures*—define how sound mediates identity, memory, and affect across different communities. Inspired by this perspective, Paulo C. Chagas undertook fieldwork in 2019 across five culturally and acoustically distinct regions: São Paulo (Brazil), Riverside (USA), Pune (India), Mannheim (Germany), and Moscow (Russia). Equipped with a Sennheiser AMBEO ambisonic microphone and an Insta360 ONE X camera, he captured 360-degree video and spatial audio from urban, sacred, natural, and social environments. The recording process foregrounded a first-person methodology [41], treating the mobile setup not merely as a recording device but as an extension of embodied perception—receptive to cultural affect and acoustic nuance. In this sense, the project approaches immersive and telematic composition as a space for intercultural resonance, where diverse *listening cultures* engage, overlap, and invite reflection.

The artistic outcomes of the project include the large-scale installation *Sound Imaginations: Audiovisual Immersive Installation*, exhibited at the Culver Center of the Arts in Riverside from February 29 to March 5, 2020 [10]. This work

integrated ambisonic sound and 360° video recorded in São Paulo, Riverside, Pune, Mannheim, and Moscow into a unified spatial composition. Developed in collaboration with curator Nikolay Maslov, the installation created a polyphonic environment in which images and sounds from different locations were combined, destabilizing fixed associations between place, identity, and perception. As Sandra Baltazar noted, the installation invited audiences to “listen with their eyes and see with their ears,” emphasizing perceptual ambiguity and intercultural resonance as central artistic strategies [2].

Building upon this immersive installation, the extended project culminated in the feature-length film *Sound Imaginations: Telematic Immersion* (2024) [20], developed in collaboration with the Brazilian flutist and researcher Cássia Carrascoza. Whereas the installation foregrounded field recordings and audiovisual montage, the film focused on the performative and telematic dimensions of the project, enacting what Chagas has termed the *telematic paradigm*. The film brings together four major works for flute, live-electronics, and 360° video—*Mojave*, *Virtual Studies* (version 2), *I Hear You Breathe*, and *Sound Imaginations Improvisations*—each reflecting different aspects of asynchronous polyphony, real-time transformation, and distributed performance. As Chagas recently discussed, the telematic environment does not simply mediate distance but generates new forms of presence and resonance across geographic and technological thresholds [19].

The collaboration with Cássia Carrascoza was essential for this exploration. Her improvisational fluency and sensorial awareness brought life to the material, forging a subtle balance between human expression and machine mediation. In the telematic setting, performer and sound are no longer anchored to a single spatial node but are multiplied through networked interfaces, immersive projection, and real-time spatial diffusion. Situating *Sound Imaginations* within what he terms the *telematic paradigm*, Chagas describes an extension of the electroacoustic paradigm in which the distinction between presence and absence, local and remote, collapses into a shared acoustic and visual field [13]. Drawing on Vilém Flusser’s notion of dialogical networks [26], Jacques Attali’s symbolic functions of music [1], and Byung-Chul Han’s critique of ritual erosion [28,29], he argues that telematic art reclaims symbolic and communal dimensions of ritual in a time of fragmentation. Rather than presenting ritual as fixed, *Sound Imaginations* enacts it as a fluid and polyphonic exchange—an aesthetic gesture that produces intimacy and recognition across distances. In this sense, the project proposes not only new models for composition and performance but also for being-together in mediated environments. Listening becomes a relational act of resonance, reverberating across bodies, places, and screens.

8 From Cybernetics to Immersivity: Paradigm Shifts in Sound Space

The paradigm of cybernetics, as analyzed by Friedrich Kittler, marked a decisive transformation in the ways communication, knowledge, and human subjectivity

were understood [31]. For Kittler, the rise of cybernetics and information theory displaced earlier modes of interpretation rooted in philosophy, poetry, and hermeneutics. Meaning was no longer sought through discursive depth or symbolic mediation, but through feedback, signal-to-noise ratios, and stochastic systems. This shift, originating in military technologies of prediction and control, redefined human beings less as autonomous subjects than as components within machine circuits—“machine-objects” governed by probabilistic processes.

In this cybernetic worldview, noise is not simply an obstacle to be eliminated, but the very condition from which information emerges. Claude Shannon’s foundational theory defined communication precisely as “the selection from noise” [37], while Norbert Wiener’s wartime work on anti-aircraft prediction bound human nervous systems into feedback loops with machines [42]. Kittler underscores that in such a system, the interpretative role of the subject is neutralized: humans no longer constitute the origin of meaning but become elements in chains of control, interception, and signal processing.

Against this background, the emergence of *immersivity* signals another profound shift—one that repositions space, body, and cognition within an expanded field. Immersivity does not simply extend cybernetic feedback; it integrates physical and virtual dimensions, conscious and unconscious processes, embodied affect and machinic agency. As Katherine Hayles has argued, *cognitive assemblages* comprise not only human consciousness but also nonconscious operations distributed across technical systems and environments [30]. Immersive space therefore becomes a cognitive-affective field in which subjectivity is co-constituted by bodies, machines, and networks.

To grasp *immersivity* in this broad sense is to recognize a *double movement*: on one hand, immersive technologies can deepen relational presence, intimacy, and creativity; on the other, they can replicate the cybernetic logics of prediction, control, and surveillance. As shown in Section 5, algorithmic listening systems, AI-driven monitoring, and sonic crowd-control devices extend the vibrational model of domination into everyday environments. Sound becomes not only a spectacular tool of violence but a subtle medium of governance, where listening itself is captured, analyzed, and weaponized.

What is at stake, then, is the *future of immersion*. The vibrational forces at play in immersive environments hold both destructive and generative potentials. They can annihilate subjectivity, as in sonic torture, or they can sustain intimacy, creativity, and collective presence. This ambivalence demands ethical vigilance: immersive sound practices are never neutral, for they always enact power over bodies and minds, whether to heal or to harm, to create spaces of resonance and resistance, or to reproduce systems of terror and control.

9 Conclusion

Sound space in electroacoustic music is not merely a technical parameter or a stylistic concern—it is a critical field where aesthetics, cognition, and politics intersect. This article has traced the transformation of sound space from fixed

studio constructs to immersive, distributed, and relational environments. From the cybernetic feedback systems in *Projektion* [6] to the affective rupture of *The Refrigerator* [8], and from the immersive spatiality of *Pune Metamorphosis* [15] to the global polyphony of *Sound Imaginations* [20], each work examined contributes to a redefinition of what it means to compose, listen, and be present in sound.

As argued in Section 8, *From Cybernetics to Immersivity: Paradigm Shifts in Sound Space*, this transformation is not only aesthetic but paradigmatic. Kittler reminds us that cybernetics emerged from war, from the attempt to calculate signals against noise, integrating humans into feedback loops of prediction and control [31]. This paradigm shifted the foundations of communication away from interpretation and hermeneutics, recasting humans as machine-objects in probabilistic systems. Today, however, we inhabit a different state: that of *immersivity*. Here, space is no longer external but enveloping; it integrates the physical and the virtual, conscious and nonconscious processes, what Hayles describes as *cognitive assemblages* [30]. Immersivity thus names not only a spatial experience but a new condition of subjectivity, in which human beings, machines, and environments form interdependent systems of resonance and control.

This recognition raises urgent *political and ethical choices*. As Section 5 showed, the same vibrational logics that can annihilate subjectivity through torture or surveillance also sustain intimacy, creativity, and collective presence. Algorithmic listening, AI-driven monitoring, and sonic crowd-control technologies demonstrate how immersion can be weaponized, transforming listening into a site of governance. Yet immersive practices can also generate counter-spaces—fields of resistance, care, and solidarity—where sound is a medium of encounter rather than domination.

What emerges is a vision of sound space as a *medium of encounter and decision*: between self and system, body and environment, memory and technology. This conception aligns with contemporary theories of non-human cognition, affective resonance, and situated knowledge. In particular, the telematic paradigm opens a pathway toward collective sonic presence, challenging the boundaries of geography, identity, and authorship.

In a time when technological mediation both fragments and connects, electroacoustic composition offers not only tools for aesthetic innovation but also frameworks for political reflection and ontological inquiry. To compose immersive sound space is to participate in shaping the conditions of perception, relation, and power. The choice is not whether immersion will define our present and future, but *how* it will be shaped—toward control and domination, or toward creativity, intimacy, and freedom.

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